

EVOLUTION OF CARE PATHWAYS IN CLINICAL PRACTICE GUIDELINES FOR HEART FAILURE: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW WITH NARRATIVE SYNTHESIS

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Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study. The research was conducted independently, and no financial, commercial, or personal relationships influenced the design, execution, or conclusions of this work. All authors have reviewed and approved the final version of the manuscript, and there were no external pressures from sponsors or organizations during the development of this study.

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ABSTRACT

Introduction and objectives: The Clinical Practice Guidelines (CPG) for heart failure (HF) from the European Society of Cardiology (ESC) and the American Heart Association (AHA) have reflected significant changes in HF patient care over the last two decades. This study aims to conduct a systematic review with narrative synthesis of these CPGs to describe the current components of the HF patient care pathway and its evolution since 2000.

Methods: A systematic review was conducted following the PRISMA 2020 statement, registered in PROSPERO (CRD42024551462). CPGs from the ESC and AHA published between 2000 and 2023, containing recommendations for the management of HF in adults, were included. Methodological quality was assessed using the AGREE II tool. Class I recommendations were extracted for thematic analysis of the key components of the care pathway.

Results: A total of 14 CPGs were included in the review. Methodological quality showed continuous improvement. The number of recommendations increased by 344.6% over two decades. Five key components of the care pathway were identified: 1) initial assessment and diagnosis, 2) pharmacological and non-pharmacological treatment, 3) comorbidity management, 4) multidisciplinary management, and 5) management of patients hospitalized for acute HF.

Conclusions: HF CPGs have evolved significantly, improving their quality and expanding recommendations that outline the optimal care pathway for patients. However, the increase in the number of recommendations may hinder their applicability in clinical practice, presenting the challenge of facilitating their implementation in complex healthcare systems.

MeSH Terms: heart failure, clinical practice guidelines, systematic review, pharmacological treatment.

Abbreviations:

- **AHA:** American Heart Association
- **CPGs:** Clinical Practice Guidelines
- **ESC:** European Society of Cardiology
- **LEVF:**Left Ventricular Ejection Fraction
- **HF:** Heart Failure
- **LoE:** Level of Evidence

1. INTRODUCTION and OBJECTIVES

The paradigm shift that has occurred in the care of patients with Heart Failure (HF) over the past 20 years is reflected in the evolution and content of the Clinical Practice Guidelines (CPGs) published by both the European Society of Cardiology (ESC) and the American Heart Association (AHA)-American College of Cardiology (ACC)-Heart Failure Society of America (HFSA)^{1,2}. Both documents are the global reference for professionals responsible for the care of HF patients, serving as a foundation for the development of national CPGs, and jointly encompassing evidence-based recommendations for patient care. In this way, the optimal care pathway that HF patients should experience within the healthcare system is shaped (understood as one that complies with all the key recommendations from clinical practice guidelines, adhering to the highest level of evidence available during each period). The components of this pathway have undergone significant growth and evolution, driven by advances in disease management³ and the need to respond to the increasing complexity of patients⁴.

A systematic review (SR) that includes a temporal analysis of these CPGs can help us evaluate their methodological quality, recognize progress in HF management, and identify the areas where the most significant changes have occurred, while also highlighting undervalued aspects that could be improved in future publications.

The aim of this work is to conduct a SR with narrative synthesis of the CPGs, to describe the current components of the HF patient care pathway and how it has evolved over the past two decades, evaluating newly incorporated themes as well as recommendations that have been removed.

2. METHOD

This SR was designed in accordance with the 2020 PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) statement and was registered in PROSPERO (CRD42024551462).

2.1 PICAR Question

What are the key components of the care pathway for heart failure (HF) patients reflected in the CPGs, and how have the published recommendations evolved from 2000 to the present?.

The study selection criteria were chosen based on the characteristics of the PICAR framework⁵:

Population: Patients \geq 18 years old with a primary diagnosis of HF.

Intervention: Review of CPGs published between 2000 and 2023 by the ESC/AHA.

Comparison: Comparison of recommendations over time.

Outcomes: Key components of the care pathway and their evolution.

To comprehensively analyze and synthesize the existing evidence regarding the PICAR question presented, inclusion and exclusion criteria for studies were established:

Inclusion Criteria:

CPGs published by the ESC/AHA from 2000-01-01 to 2023-12-31 containing recommendations on the management of HF.

Exclusion Criteria:

CPGs developed for a non-adult population, consensus documents, recommendations from scientific societies, or local protocols that were not published by the ESC/AHA.

2.2 Information Sources and Search Strategy

The search was conducted in the electronic libraries PubMed and Scopus (the full search strategy, including search terms, Boolean operators, and filters applied is available in Supplementary Material 1).

2.3 Study Selection

A standardised summary sheet was created to compile all key data from each study (title, author, abstract, PMID or DOI, and an internally assigned ID) that appeared in the bibliographic search across the different sources. Several rounds of screening and review were conducted to select all publications that met the inclusion criteria. After removing duplicates, two reviewers independently screened the titles and abstracts of the identified guidelines to assess their eligibility based on the inclusion/exclusion criteria. Any discrepancies in the study selection between the two primary reviewers (RQ and NJ) were resolved by a third reviewer (FE). A second round of screening was then applied, during which a primary reviewer (JG) read the articles to determine whether they could be selected for data extraction.

2.4 Data Extraction

Data from the selected guidelines were independently extracted by two reviewers (RQ and NJ) using a customized data collection form (approved by all authors). The primary reviewer (RQ) conducted the data extraction, and a second reviewer (NJ) verified a random sample of 15% of the extracted data records to verify the accuracy of the extraction process.

2.5 Quality Assessment of the CPGs

The quality of the guidelines was assessed using the AGREE II tool, which evaluates aspects of

the design and execution of CPGs using 23 items distributed across six domains⁶. These scores were then normalized to a percentage scale to facilitate comparison between the guidelines. The normalized scores were categorized into low quality (0-30%), moderate quality (31-60%), and high quality (61-100%)⁷. In case of discrepancies, a consensus decision was reached between the two reviewers (RQ and NJ).

2.6 Data Synthesis

All recommendations from the CPGs were extracted for descriptive and traceability purposes, but only class 1 recommendations (with any level of evidence) were included in the synthesis to focus on those applicable to most HF patients and relevant to the care pathway.

A recommendation matrix was developed for comparison, categorization, and summarization. Each matrix had seven columns representing the level of evidence for the publication periods (2001, 2005, 2008/9, 2012/13, 2016/17, and 2021/23), with each row containing a recommendation. To avoid duplication, recommendations from the ESC and AHA CPGs were combined, eliminating similar entries.

Thematic analysis was used to identify thematic codes for the HF care pathway components, allowing patterns to emerge naturally from the data⁸. The coding process was independently conducted by two reviewers (RQ, NJ), and discrepancies were resolved through discussion with a third reviewer (FE).

2.7 Justification for the Narrative Approach

A narrative synthesis was chosen to integrate and contextualize CPG recommendations over a broad time period. Unlike a quantitative meta-analysis, which focuses on summarizing data, narrative synthesis allows for the inclusion of qualitative information, providing detailed discussions of trends and clinical reasoning over time. This approach is especially useful for

capturing nuances in complex or divergent recommendations that might be missed in a more rigid analysis⁹.

2.8 Ethical Considerations

This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles established for systematic literature reviews¹⁰, as well as the international recommendations on clinical research present in the Declaration of Helsinki. Consent was not required, as no individual patient data were included. All the CPGs included are documents published by recognized entities and publicly accessible, ensuring respect for copyright and intellectual property rights.

3. RESULTS

A total of 1,100 records were identified, with 14 CPGs included after duplicates were removed, and titles and abstracts screened. Sixty-four were excluded for not being ESC/AHA CPGs or not addressing HF management (Figure 1).

Quality of the Included Guidelines

The methodological quality of the CPGs, assessed with the AGREE II tool, showed continuous improvement across all domains. The AHA guidelines increased their overall quality score from 80.4% in 2001 to 94.4% in 2022, while ESC guidelines improved from 79.5% to 95% in 2023. The applicability domain, though improved from 18.5 to 23.5 points out of 28, scored lower than other domains. The complete quality analysis is available on Zenodo (open access digital repository)¹¹.

Evolution of the Number and Type of Recommendations

The total number of recommendations increased from 65 (52.3% class I, 26.1% class II, and 21.5% class III) in the 2001 period to 289 in the 2021/23 period (46.3% class I, 43.2% class II, and 10.3% class III), representing a 344.6% increase over the past two decades (figure 2).

Thematic Analysis of the Heart Failure Care Pathway

The thematic analysis identified five fundamental components that structure the optimal care pathway for HF patients within the CPGs (Figure 3). The first component was "initial assessment and diagnosis," which included aspects related to patient history, physical examination, laboratory tests, and imaging to diagnose and phenotype patients. The second identified component was "pharmacological and non-pharmacological treatment," structured according to the Left Ventricular Ejection Fraction (LVEF) value. The third block of the care pathway involved the management of comorbidities, with special attention to hypertension, atrial fibrillation, diabetes mellitus, anemia, and valvular disease. The fourth component focused on "multidisciplinary management," which included recommendations related to HF programs, patient education, care transitions, advanced-stage care, etc. Finally, the differentiated recommendations for the "management of patients hospitalized for acute HF" represented the fifth essential component of the care pathway identified in the thematic analysis.

Recommendations and Their Evolution in CPGs

Initial Assessment and Diagnosis. Regarding the initial assessment, the CPGs from the period 2001 to 2012/2013 included specific class I recommendations that indicated the need for a thorough medical history, physical examination (including vital signs), along with the evaluation of congestion, the patient's ability to perform daily activities, and the identification of the possible etiology and trigger of HF. In the 2016/2017 period, many of these recommendations were removed and do not appear in current documents, where the only class I (LoE C) recommendation is the need to document the NYHA functional classification.

Laboratory study recommendations have consistently included, from the initial period to the present, the determination of a complete blood count, urinalysis, serum electrolytes, blood urea nitrogen, serum creatinine, glucose, lipid profile, liver function tests, iron studies, and the measurement of thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH). In the 2012/2013 period, the

determination of natriuretic peptides in various scenarios was added as a basic concept, a recommendation that remains valid (LoE A), along with tests aimed at diagnosing cardiac amyloidosis (2021/23 period) (LoE B).

In terms of imaging studies, ECG (LoE C) and echocardiography (LoE C) are present in all analyzed periods. Additionally, from the 2012/2013 period to the present, chest X-ray (LoE C) is recommended. Current guidelines include the recommendation to perform cardiac MRI in patients where echocardiographic evaluation is not possible or when infiltrative disease is suspected (LoE C). Coronary angiography is recommended for patients with angina (LoE B), and right heart catheterization is recommended for patients who are candidates for lung transplantation or mechanical support therapies (LoE C).

Table 1 shows the essential current components for initial assessment and diagnosis in the care pathway and their evolution over time.

Pharmacological Treatment (Table 2). In patients with reduced ejection fraction (HFrEF), CPGs have consistently recommended, from 2001 to the present, the use of ACEIs/ARBs, aldosterone antagonists (both with LoE A), and diuretics for congestion relief and symptom improvement (LoE B) as class I recommendations. The recommendation to use beta-blockers (LoE A) began in the 2005 period. The use of ARNIs is more recent, introduced in the 2016/2017 period to replace ACEIs/ARBs (LoE B), reaching LoE A in the 2021/23 period for patients with NYHA functional class II-III. The fourth pillar of treatment for HFrEF patients, SGLT-2 inhibitors, emerged only in the current period, 2021/23, though with LoE A from the outset. Additionally, there is a current IA recommendation for the use of hydralazine and isosorbide dinitrate in African American patients with NYHA III-IV who are already on optimized therapy, a recommendation that began in the 2012/2013 period (LoE B). Treatment with digoxin, which was present in the CPGs of the early periods, was removed from class I recommendations in the 2008/09 period. Finally, in the 2021/23 period, there is a new class I recommendation for titrating indicated treatments to target doses, based on patient tolerance (LoE A).

Class I recommendations for pharmacological treatment of HFmrEF patients are very recent in the CPGs, limited to diuretics (LoE B) from the 2016/2017 period and the use of SGLT-2 inhibitors (LoE A) from 2021/23. A similar trend is observed in HFpEF patients, where the use of SGLT-2 inhibitors emerged in the 2021/23 period (LoE A), though diuretics have been present since the initial 2001 period to the present with LoE C (due to their early inclusion in AHA guidelines). In both groups, HFmrEF and HFpEF, current guidelines recommend using a second thiazide diuretic in patients on medium-high doses of loop diuretics to prevent electrolyte disturbances (LoE B).

Additionally, the current CPGs (2021/23) include recommendations for the use of Tafamidis (LoE B) to reduce cardiovascular mortality and hospitalizations in patients with cardiac amyloidosis, regardless of LVEF.

Non-Pharmacological Treatment. The recommendations related to physical exercise and its implementation to improve quality of life and reduce the risk of hospitalizations have evolved from a LoE C in the 2005 period to a LoE A since the 2008/09 period and continuing to the present. Regarding the use of devices, while the initial period (2001) reflected uncertainty about their role in the treatment of HF patients, new studies have progressively clarified and defined the recommendations. In the current period, the guidelines provide detailed information on which patients should receive an ICD or cardiac resynchronization therapy, both with LoE A. Finally, we mention the recommendations on coronary revascularization, which are limited to cardiac surgery in the 2021/23 period (LoE B) and surgical/percutaneous techniques present only in the 2012/13 period (LoE B).

Management of Comorbidities. Class I recommendations regarding the management of anemia and/or iron deficiency, including periodic screening (LoE C) and intravenous iron treatment in HFrEF and HFmrEF (LoE A), did not appear until the current period, 2021/23. Similarly, for cancer patients, there are new recommendations concerning the evaluation of treatment in

patients who develop cardiac toxicity (LoE B) and the advisability of cardio-oncology assessment for patients at risk of toxicity (LoE C). As for the management of diabetes mellitus, recommendations from the 2008/09 period regarding glycemic control (LoE A) and the need for individualized treatment (LoE B) have been removed in later editions of the CPGs, with recommendations for the use of SGLT2-i being introduced in the 2021/23 period. Recommendations for the management of atrial fibrillation (AF) and hypertension have been consistent and numerous since the early periods. In the current guidelines, anticoagulation for AF is recommended based on thrombotic risk (LoE A), preferably with DOACs (LoE A). Regarding hypertension, the current recommendation is to optimize pharmacological treatment with a goal of achieving systolic blood pressure below 130 mmHg (LoE C), while several recommendations on pharmacological strategies from previous periods have been removed. Finally, the management of patients with valvular disease has been poorly represented in the earlier CPGs, although current guidelines provide detailed recommendations on the need for multidisciplinary evaluation of patients with valvular disease (LoE B), joint decision-making to discern between TAVI and SAVR (LoE C), and the indication of these techniques in patients with HF and severe aortic stenosis (LoE B) to reduce mortality and improve symptoms.

Multidisciplinary Management. Like the previously described components, this fourth component also encompasses various aspects of HF care (Table 3). The recommendation to enroll patients in multidisciplinary HF programs has been present since the 2001 period (LoE B) and continues in the current period (LoE A). Educating patients in self-care has been included in the CPGs, with its recommendation level progressively increasing to LoE A in the current guidelines. Additionally, it is in the current period that recommendations were introduced to review the hospitalized patient within 12 weeks (LoE C) and to plan the strategy for initiating and titrating medical treatment within the first 6 weeks after discharge (LoE B).

Hospitalized Patient with Acute HF. There were no recommendations for this component of the care pathway until the 2008/09 period. From that point onward, specific indications were gradually added to the CPGs, culminating in the current period's class I recommendations: evaluation of congestion and perfusion (LoE C) to guide diuretic therapy (LoE B), ensuring that residual congestion is always assessed before discharge (LoE C). Additionally, identifying precipitating factors and correcting reversible etiologies of HF (LoE C) is recommended. Regarding pharmacological treatment, the current recommendation is the early initiation of therapy during hospitalization in naïve patients, and the continuation of the advised therapy in patients already receiving treatment for chronic HF unless contraindicated (LoE B).

The data extraction tables for the set of CPG recommendations, as well as the recommendation matrices, are available in the supplementary material (Tables x and xx, respectively).

4. DISCUSSION

The evolution of heart failure (HF) clinical practice guidelines (CPGs) over the past two decades reflects significant scientific and technological advances, leading to a substantial increase in recommendations. This growth stems from the introduction of new pharmacological and non-pharmacological treatments¹² and a more comprehensive approach to HF patients and their comorbidities, supported by growing evidence¹³. However, this fourfold increase in recommendations poses challenges for daily clinical practice, potentially overwhelming healthcare professionals and hindering uniform implementation, which could limit their impact¹⁴.

The methodological quality of CPGs has continuously improved, as shown by AGREE II evaluations. However, the "applicability" domain remains an area for improvement, aligning with recent studies¹⁵. Despite robust recommendations, implementation is often hindered by

resource limitations, healthcare system complexities, and variability in guideline adoption. Structural barriers, such as unequal treatment access and limited resources in low-income settings, pose significant challenges¹⁶. Therefore, enhancing practical applicability should be a priority in future guidelines, focusing on necessary resources and concrete strategies for implementation.

The care pathway identified in the CPGs encompasses the necessary aspects for the proper evaluation, diagnosis, treatment, and follow-up of HF patients. In our opinion, this concept can collectively represent the activity of the healthcare system itself, in which HF patients are treated. Evaluating the impact of deviations from this pathway in terms of health outcomes can highlight its weak points, thus allowing measures to improve effectiveness¹⁷.

Several key aspects of the CPGs and their temporal analysis are worth noting. A concerning trend is the removal of essential elements of the initial assessment, such as the medical history and physical examination. While this knowledge may be considered universal, its exclusion undermines the importance of thorough clinical assessment, which remains critical in managing HF patients¹⁸. Reinforcing these basics in future guidelines could ensure a more comprehensive and accurate evaluation from the outset of care.

In the pharmacological domain, HFREF management has seen an increase in recommended drug classes, with guidelines emphasizing early treatment initiation and quickly reaching maximum tolerated doses¹⁹. The inclusion of SGLT2 inhibitors as class I recommendations for HFmrEF and HFpEF marks a milestone, paving the way for further innovations to improve outcomes²⁰. However, gaps remain in HFmrEF management recommendations.

Non-pharmacological advancements have focused on promoting physical exercise, but current CPGs should be more specific about the type and duration of recommended activity to benefit clinicians and enhance patient adherence²¹.

The management of comorbidities has gained prominence in recent guidelines, reflecting the growing complexity of HF patients²². Recommendations for managing anemia, diabetes, and cancer have increased, while chronic kidney disease remains underrepresented, signaling the need for a more comprehensive approach²³.

Gender-specific recommendations are few, likely due to limited research. The multidisciplinary approach has been reinforced, with guidelines emphasizing HF programs and team-based care, as well as temporal recommendations like post-discharge visits and medication titration, posing challenges for healthcare systems²⁴. Notably, recommendations on treatment adherence, critical for HF management success, have been removed without clear justification²⁵.

Finally, in patients hospitalized with acute HF, current CPGs emphasize the need to assess residual congestion before discharge, facilitating clinical decision-making during this critical phase²⁶. Additionally, there is a focus on coordinating post-discharge care plans to improve continuity of care across different levels of healthcare and on initiating or maintaining chronic HF therapy during hospitalization, unless contraindicated, which underscores the importance of early intervention to improve long-term outcomes²⁷.

Study Limitations

This study has several limitations. First, the focus on class I recommendations may have excluded relevant class II and III recommendations for specific subgroups. To address this, the review prioritized recommendations with general applicability to most HF patients, though this limits the full representation of available evidence. Second, only English-language guidelines were included, potentially introducing a language bias, although English CPGs represent the majority of influential international publications. Lastly, the inductive thematic analysis could have introduced reviewer bias, but an independent coding process with consensus resolution minimized this risk.

5. CONCLUSION

The HF CPGs from European and American cardiology societies have transformed over the past 20 years, improving in quality and expanding the range of management topics. This evolution outlines the care pathway for patients within the healthcare system. However, the exponential increase in recommendations may limit their real-world applicability. Future guidelines should focus on strategies to implement recommendations effectively in complex healthcare systems.

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7. FIGURES.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

8. TABLES.

Table 1. Recommendation matrix for initial clinical assessment and diagnostic class I recommendations included in the actual HF pathway.

Initial clinical assessment and diagnostics class I recommendations	CPG publication period and LOE					
	2001	2005	2008-2009	2012-2013	2016-2017	2021-2023
In patients with HF, assessment and documentation of NYHA functional classification are recommended to determine eligibility for treatments.						C-L D
In patients presenting with dyspnea, measurement of BNP or NT-proBNP is useful to support a diagnosis or exclusion of HF.				A		A
In patients with chronic HF, measurements of BNP or NT-proBNP levels are recommended for risk stratification.				A		A
In patients hospitalized for HF, measurement of BNP or NT-proBNP levels at admission is recommended to establish prognosis.				A		A
For patients who are diagnosed with HF, laboratory evaluation should include complete blood count, urinalysis, serum electrolytes, blood urea nitrogen, serum creatinine, glucose, lipid profile, liver function tests, iron studies, and thyroid-stimulating hormone to optimize management.	C	C	C	C	C	C-E O
BNP/NT-proBNP						B
Routine blood tests for comorbidities, including full blood count, urea and electrolytes, thyroid function, fasting glucose and HbA1c, lipids, iron status (TSAT and ferritin)						C
In patients presenting with dyspnea, measurement of natriuretic peptide biomarkers is useful to support a diagnosis or exclusion of HF.				A		A
Measurement of BNP or NT-proBNP is useful for establishing prognosis or disease severity in chronic HF.				A		A
Measurement of baseline levels of natriuretic peptide biomarkers and/or cardiac troponin on admission to the hospital is useful to establish a prognosis in acutely decompensated HF.				A		A
For all patients presenting with HF, a 12-lead ECG should be performed at the initial encounter to optimize management.	C	C	C	C	C	C-E O
In patients with suspected or new-onset HF, or those presenting with acute decompensated HF, a chest x-ray should be performed to assess heart size and pulmonary congestion and to detect alternative cardiac, pulmonary, and other diseases that may cause or contribute to the patient's symptoms.				C		C -LD
In patients with suspected or newly diagnosed HF, TTE should be performed during initial evaluation to assess cardiac structure and function.	C	C	C	C	C	C -LD
In patients with HF who have had a significant clinical change, or who have received GDMT and are being considered for invasive procedures or device therapy, repeat measurement of EF, degree of structural remodeling, and valvular function are useful to inform therapeutic interventions.				C		C -LD
In patients for whom echocardiography is inadequate, alternative imaging (eg, CMR, cardiac CT, radionuclide imaging) is recommended for assessment of LVEF.				C	C	C -LD
Transthoracic echocardiography.	C	C	C	C	C	C
CMR is recommended for the characterization of myocardial tissue in suspected infiltrative disease, Fabry disease, inflammatory disease (myocarditis), LV non-compaction, amyloid, sarcoidosis, iron overload/haemochromatosis.					C	C

Table 2. Recommendation matrix for the pharmacologic treatment recommendations included in the actual HF pathway.

HFrEF recommendations	2001	2005	2008 2009	2012 2013	2016 2017	2021 2023
Angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (ACEIs)						
An ACE-I is recommended for patients with HFrEF to reduce the risk of HF hospitalization and death.	A	A	A	A	A	A
In patients with previous or current symptoms of chronic HFrEF, the use of ACEi is beneficial to reduce morbidity and mortality when the use of ARNi is not feasible.						A
In patients with previous or current symptoms of chronic HFrEF, in whom ARNi is not feasible, treatment with an ACEi or ARB provides high economic value.						A
Angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs)						
The use of ARBs to reduce morbidity and mortality is recommended in patients with prior or current symptoms of chronic HFrEF who are intolerant to ACE inhibitors because of cough or angioedema.	C	A	A	A	A	A
An ARB is recommended to reduce the risk of HF hospitalization and CV death in symptomatic patients unable to tolerate an ACE-I or ARNi (patients should also receive a beta-blocker and an MRA).						B
In patients with previous or current symptoms of chronic HFrEF who are intolerant to ACEi because of cough or angioedema and when the use of ARNi is not feasible, the use of ARB is recommended to reduce morbidity and mortality.						A
Angiotensin receptor neprilysin inhibitors (ARNIs)						
In patients with HFrEF and NYHA class II to III symptoms, the use of ARNi is recommended to reduce morbidity and mortality.					B-R	A
In patients with chronic symptomatic HFrEF NYHA class II or III who tolerate an ACEi or ARB, replacement by an ARNi is recommended to further reduce morbidity and mortality.					B-R	B-R
b-Blockers						
In patients with HFrEF, with current or previous symptoms, use of 1 of the 3 beta blockers proven to reduce mortality (eg, bisoprolol, carvedilol, sustained-release metoprolol succinate) is recommended to reduce mortality and hospitalizations.		A	A	A	A	A
A beta-blocker is recommended, in addition an ACE-I, for patients with stable, symptomatic HFrEF to reduce the risk of HF hospitalization and death.		A	A	A	A	A
In patients with HFrEF, with current or previous symptoms, beta-blocker therapy provides high economic value.						A
Aldosterone antagonists						
In patients with HFrEF and NYHA class II to IV symptoms, an MRA (spironolactone or eplerenone) is recommended to reduce morbidity and mortality, if eGFR is >30 mL/min/1.73 m ² and serum potassium is <5.0 mEq/L. Careful monitoring of potassium, renal function, and diuretic dosing should be performed at initiation and closely monitored thereafter to minimize risk of hyperkalemia and renal insufficiency.	B	B	B	A	A	A
In patients with HFrEF and NYHA class II to IV symptoms, MRA therapy provides high economic value.						A
Sodium-glucose co-transporter 2 inhibitors						
In patients with symptomatic chronic HFrEF, SGLT2i are recommended to reduce hospitalization for HF and cardiovascular mortality, irrespective of the presence of type 2 diabetes.						A
In patients with symptomatic chronic HFrEF, SGLT2i therapy provides intermediate economic value.						A

Diuretics						
In patients with HF who have fluid retention, diuretics are recommended to relieve congestion, improve symptoms, and prevent worsening HF.	A	C	B	B	B	B-N R
For patients with HF and congestive symptoms, addition of a thiazide (eg, metolazone) to treatment with a loop diuretic should be reserved for patients who do not respond to moderate or high-dose loop diuretics to minimize electrolyte abnormalities.						B-N R
Other therapies						
Hydralazine and Isosorbide Dinitrate For patients self-identified as African American with NYHA class III-IV HFrEF who are receiving optimal medical therapy, the combination of hydralazine and isosorbide dinitrate is recommended to improve symptoms and reduce morbidity and mortality.			B	A		A
For patients self-identified as African American with NYHA class III to IV HFrEF who are receiving optimal medical therapy with ACEi or ARB, beta blockers, and MRA, the combination of hydralazine and isosorbide dinitrate provides high economic value.						A
HFmrEF recommendations	200 1	200 5	200 8 200 9	201 2 201 3	201 6 201 7	202 1 202 3
An SGLT2 inhibitor (dapagliflozin or empagliflozin) is recommended in patients with HFmrEF to reduce the risk of HF hospitalization or CV death.						A
In patients with HF who have fluid retention, diuretics are recommended to relieve congestion, improve symptoms, and prevent worsening HF.						B-N R
For patients with HF and congestive symptoms, addition of a thiazide (eg, metolazone) to treatment with a loop diuretic should be reserved for patients who do not respond to moderate or high-dose loop diuretics to minimize electrolyte abnormalities.						B-N R
In patients with HFimpEF after treatment, GDMT should be continued to prevent relapse of HF and LV dysfunction, even in patients who may become asymptomatic						B-R
Diuretics are recommended in patients with congestion and HFmrEF in order to alleviate symptoms and signs.					B	C
it is recommended to screen patients with HFpEF or HFmrEF for both cardiovascular and noncardiovascular comorbidities, which, if present, should be treated provided safe and effective interventions exist to improve symptoms, well-being and/or prognosis.					C	
HFpEF recommendations	200 1	200 5	200 8 200 9	201 2 201 3	201 6 201 7	202 1 202 3
An SGLT2 inhibitor is recommended in patients with HFpEF to reduce the risk of HF hospitalization or cardiovascular death.						A
For patients with HF and congestive symptoms, addition of a thiazide (eg, metolazone) to treatment with a loop diuretic should be reserved for patients who do not respond to moderate or high-dose loop diuretics to minimize electrolyte abnormalities.						B-N R
In patients with HFimpEF after treatment, GDMT should be continued to prevent relapse of HF and LV dysfunction, even in patients who may become asymptomatic.						B-R
Patients with HFpEF and hypertension should have medication titrated to attain blood pressure targets in accordance with published clinical practice guidelines to prevent morbidity.	A					C-L D
Screening for, and treatment of, aetiologies, and cardiovascular and non-cardiovascular comorbidities is recommended in patients with HFpEF.						C
Diuretics are recommended in congested patients with HFpEF in order to alleviate symptoms and signs.	C	C	C	C	C	C
All LVEF	200 1	200 5	200 8 200 9	201 2 201 3	201 6 201 7	202 1 202 3
In select patients with wild-type or variant transthyretin cardiac amyloidosis and NYHA class I to III HF symptoms, transthyretin tetramer						B-R

stabilizer therapy (tafamidis) is indicated to reduce cardiovascular morbidity and mortality.						
Tafamidis is recommended in patients with genetic testing proven hTTR-CA and NYHA class I or II symptoms to reduce symptoms, CV hospitalization and mortality.						B
Tafamidis is recommended in patients with wtTTR-CA and NYHA class I or II symptoms to reduce symptoms, CV hospitalization and mortality.						B

Table 3. Recommendation matrix for multidisciplinary care class I recommendations included in the actual HF pathway.

Multidisciplinary care recommendations	2001	2005	2008 2009	2012 2013	2016 2017	2021 2023
In patients with HFrEF, titration of guideline directed medication dosing to achieve target doses showed to be efficacious in RCTs is recommended, to reduce cardiovascular mortality and HF hospitalizations, unless not well tolerated.						A
In patients with high-risk HF, particularly those with recurrent hospitalizations for HFrEF, referral to multidisciplinary HF disease management programs is recommended to reduce the risk of hospitalization.						B-R
In patients hospitalized with worsening HF, patient-centered discharge instructions with a clear plan for transitional care should be provided before hospital discharge.				C		B-N R
It is recommended that HF patients are enrolled in a multidisciplinary HF management programme to reduce the risk of HF hospitalization and mortality.	B	B	A	A	A	A
Structured follow up schedule	2001	2005	2008 2009	2012 2013	2016 2017	2021 2023
An intensive strategy of initiation and rapid up-titration of evidence-based treatment before discharge and during frequent and careful follow-up visits in the first 6 weeks following a HF hospitalization is recommended to reduce the risk of HF rehospitalization or death.						B
An early follow-up visit is recommended at 12 weeks after discharge to assess signs of congestion, drug tolerance and start and/or up titrate evidence-based therapy.						C
Self-care recommendations	2001	2005	2008 2009	2012 2013	2016 2017	2021 2023
Patients with HF should receive specific education and support to facilitate HF self-care in a multidisciplinary manner.		C		B		B-R
Self-management strategies are recommended to reduce the risk of HF hospitalization and mortality.						A

9. SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL.

Supplementary Material 1.

Detailed Search Strategy

The following search strategy was used to identify relevant clinical practice guidelines (CPGs) on heart failure published between January 1, 2000, and January 1, 2024. Searches were conducted in PubMed and Scopus databases, using controlled vocabulary and free-text terms combined with Boolean operators. The search structure applied in each database is detailed below:

1. PubMed

The following search strategy was used:

Search Terms:

("heart failure"[MeSH Terms] OR "heart failure"[All Fields])
AND ("practice guidelines as topic"[MeSH Terms] OR "guidelines"[All Fields])
AND ("European Society of Cardiology"[All Fields] OR "American Heart Association"[All Fields]
OR "American College of Cardiology"[All Fields] OR "Heart Failure Society of America"[All Fields])

Filters applied:

- Language: English
- Publication dates: January 1, 2000, to January 1, 2024
- Publication type: Clinical Practice Guidelines

2. Scopus

The search strategy was adapted for this database, considering different indexing formats:

Search Terms:

TITLE-ABS-KEY ("heart failure" AND "guidelines" AND ("European Society of Cardiology" OR "American Heart Association" OR "American College of Cardiology" OR "Heart Failure Society of America"))

Filters applied:

- Language: English
- Publication dates: 2000-2024
- Document type: Guidelines

3. Exclusion Based on Language and Access

Language: Publications in languages other than English were excluded, as major international guidelines are predominantly published in English. We acknowledge that this exclusion may limit the inclusion of local guidelines not translated into English, which is considered a limitation of this study.

Access: In cases where full-text documents were not accessible through institutional subscriptions, attempts were made to contact the authors or relevant scientific societies to obtain access to the necessary documents.

4. Boolean Operator Combination

Boolean operators were used in both cases to combine search terms and ensure relevant results:

- **AND:** To ensure results included all specified terms (e.g., "heart failure" and "guidelines").

- **OR:** To include synonyms or variants (e.g., "European Society of Cardiology" OR "American Heart Association").
- **NOT:** No NOT operator was used to avoid inadvertently excluding potentially relevant studies.

5. Results and Screening

Search results were compiled, and duplicates were removed before screening. The titles and abstracts were independently reviewed by two authors (RQ and NJ) to assess eligibility, with a third reviewer (FE) resolving any discrepancies.